

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybider Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildirimler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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Turkish Films and Social Psychology: Socio-Psychological Presentation in *Gülen Adam* (1989)

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Abstract

To understand the socio-psychological dynamics of Turkish society, Kemal Sunal's films constitute an important source of social knowledge in modern artistic and literary studies. With his humorous style and deep character analysis, Sunal effectively reflects the social and cultural structure of Türkiye. In the films, he has acted in, the life struggles of ordinary individuals, social criticism and humorous elements combine to offer a rich socio-psychological perspective.

While expressing the characters of theatre and film artist Sunal in a humorous way, including their economic difficulties, the changing education system, cultural differences, social injustices, and conflicts with societal norms, the aim is to instill a deep sense of empathy in the audience. The use of humour as a tool for social criticism is one of the most prominent features of the works in which Sunal appeared.

Sunal's characters offer an important perspective for understanding the social structure of Turkish society and the place of individuals within this structure, and are considered cultural and artistic texts that contain deep social and psychological layers. The characters brought to life by Sunal are significant cultural, literary, historical, economic, and artistic legacies that provide viewers with a thought-provoking perspective.

Sunal's films address the most defining and important elements of social psychology by exploring individuals' conformity to social values, their differences, their struggles to find their identities, and their battles against social change. In this context, the study examines the psychological depth of the characters and their relationship with social norms in terms of the impact they have on viewers.

This study aims to illustrate how society is reflected through the individual by examining the socio-psychological framework of Yusuf, an ordinary citizen, and the self-found solutions he discovered during the process of societal and economic change, using the modern work *Gülen Adam* (1989) as an example. Without criticising a specific form of government, the individual aims to present how the general effects of a particular situation are reflected in the public.

Keywords: Literature, Socio-psychology, Turkish Films and Turkish Culture

Türk Filmleri ve Toplum Psikolojisi: *Gülen Adam* (1989) Filminde Sosyo-Psikolojik Sunum

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Özet

Kemal Sunal'ın filmleri Türk toplumunun sosyo-psikolojik dinamiklerini anlamak açısından Modern dönem sanatsal ve edebi çalışmalarda önemli bir sosyal bilgi kaynak teşkil etmektedir. Sunal, mizahi üslubu ve derin karakter analizleriyle Türkiye'nin sosyal ve kültürel yapısını etkili bir biçimde yansıtmaktadır. Rol almış olduğu filmlerde, sıradan bireylerin yaşam mücadeleleri, toplumsal eleştiriler ve mizahi unsurlar birleşerek zengin bir sosyo-psikolojik anlamda geniş bir açı sunmaktadır.

Tiyatro ve film sanatçısı Sunal'ın karakterleri, ekonomik zorlukları, eğitim sisteminin değişimini, kültürel farklılıkları, sosyal adaletsizlikleri ve toplumsal normlarla çatışmalarını mizahi bir dille ifade ederken, izleyicilere derin bir empati duygusu kazandırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Mizahın toplumsal eleştiri için bir araç olarak kullanılması, Sunal'ın yer almış olduğu eserlerin en belirgin özelliklerinden biridir.

Sunal'ın karakterleri, Türk toplumunun sosyal yapısını ve bireylerin bu yapı içindeki yerini anlamaya yönelik önemli bir perspektif sunmakta, derin toplumsal ve psikolojik katmanlar barındıran kültürel ve sanatsal metinler olarak değerlendirilmektedir. Sunal'ın hayat verdiği karakterleri, izleyicilere düşündürücü bir bakış açısı kazandıran önemli birer kültürel, edebi, tarihsel, ekonomik ve sanatsal miraslar niteliğindedir.

Sunal'ın filmleri, bireylerin toplumsal değerlerle uyumunu, farklılığını, kimlik bulma çabalarını ve toplumsal değişim karşısında verdikleri mücadeleleri ele alarak, toplum psikolojisinin belirleyici en önemli unsurlarını ortaya koymaktadır. Bu bağlamda, çalışmada karakterlerin psikolojik derinlikleri ve toplumsal normlarla olan ilişkileri, izleyiciler üzerinde bıraktığı etki açısından incelenmektedir.

Bu çalışma sıradan bir vatandaş olan Yusuf'un toplum ve ekonominin değişkenliği sürecinde kendi kendine bulunduğu çözümlerin sosyo-psikolojik çerçeve ele alınmasıyla, birey üzerinden toplumun nasıl yansıtıldığını modern dönem eseri olan *Gülen Adam* (1989) üzerinden anlatmayı amaçlamaktadır. Belirli bir hükümet biçimini eleştirmeden, birey belirli bir durumun genel etkilerinin genele nasıl yansıdığını sunmayı amaçlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Edebiyat, Sosyo-psikoloji, Türk Filmleri ve Türk Kültürü

Introduction

In 20th century's Türkiye, sociological study, which is the common subject of both cinema and literature, has been a common subject in recent academic studies, especially the adaptation of literary books to cinema or the socio-psychological presentation of characters in cinema. The tragic, comical and dramatic treatment of the subjects of the work find direction in the audience as self-knowledge or learning the social order.

In the recognition of the social order, Kemal Sunal, who starred in nearly a hundred films of Turkish cinema, is a great cinema artist in terms of representing the people as one of them. The films he starred in and the

socio-psychological presentations of the people of Türkiye are still as valid today as they were in his own years.

Some of Kemal Sunal films, such as *Hababam Class* (1974), shows the signs of the deterioration in education and its gradual deterioration; *Davaro* (1981) shows how rural people are oppressed by concepts such as agha or banditry; *Orta Direk Şaban* (1984) presents the effects of class differences in society on individuals. And each film presents almost completely different sociological issues to the audience. In this study, in the film *Gülen Adam* (1989), we see Yusuf, a lower class person who reacts with laughter to all kinds of sad situations, the cost of living and even to people who point out to him that love can be realised according to class status. Yusuf sociologically describes the real lives of people and in this framework, he presents socio-psychological perceptions with ironic descriptions.

Individual presentations in Turkish cinema are actually both indirect and direct presentations of social life. In the research study, entitled *Yeni Sağ Siyaset, Ekonomi ve Toplum Anlayışının Türk Sinemasındaki İzleri: Politik Komedi Filmleri Odağında Bir Değerlendirme* (2021), it is explained that cinema, which is a part of art, is also a means of mass communication and is preserved as a social document in almost all areas of society and is presented as a reflection of the economic, moral, social and cultural processes that Türkiye has undergone. Cinema is a social common point gathers people on their especially to present and comment on the cultural and individual perceptions. In Kemal Sunal films, the common points are so general that almost everyone can find an issue relates to him or her.

Turkish cinema actors such as Kemal Sunal, Şener Şen and İlyas Salman took roles in the presentation of the economic and sociological reflection of the New Right Politics, which originated in the USA and England and started in the 1980s, and presented the individual's personal influences on the white screen (Sarı, 2021). The reflection of the formation of individual will or economic freedom in the economy, the foundations of which were laid in Europe and America in the 1970s, on Türkiye's economic and political understandings has been a long period of twenty years, ending in 1990. The presentation of these insights to the public by the cinema, which is in the center of Türkiye's transition to these understandings, has of course also required a process. However, what is known is that the aim of improving the Turkish economy and politics has always evolved in a complex way with new searches.

As these efforts were made in each period, society and its smallest structure, the individual, was always deeply affected by. And if we compare it to the previous decades, in the 1950s, 1960s and 1970s, cinema was mostly based on family, culture and interpersonal relations, with no political content. After the 1980s, political and economic processes began to be reflected in the cinema. Distinct groups such as good-bad, rich-poor, village-city and village-city, which are no longer in a community but in two sides, have been seen in cinema with their sharp features and political extensions in films (Sarı, 221).

The aim of this study is not to criticize a particular form of government, but to examine the effects and perceptions of Türkiye's economic and political processes on the individual from a socio-political (or socio-psychological) perspective. It is aimed to show that these processes can create a negative evolution in the individual, that it is possible to have adverse reactions to events and how the individual is affected by the general situation of the society, how he internalizes it, how he makes it a norm and adapts it to a general interaction area.

Kemal Sunal does not appear as an extremely well-groomed, handsome or rich character like the Yeşil Çam actors, but rather as a character whose class difference is a little more distant from the public and whose class difference is drawn with certain lines, but rather as a middling dressed and not very handsome character who does not feel obliged to look decent in terms of appearance. This is the first key that shows how the economic depression of the people is reflected in both their personal and psychological existence.

In this study, Kemal Sunal's representation in cinema and his socio-psychological effects on the public are analysed through qualitative research method. The research is primarily based on the analysis of one of Sunal's most well-known films, *Gülen Adam* (1989) and the character of Yusuf. The socio-economic status of Yusuf and other characters in this film, their interaction with social norms and their psychological reflections on the audience are evaluated. In addition, Sunal's place and positive effects in the society are explained through the academic and literary study.

In conclusion, this study not only aims to understand the effects of Kemal Sunal's works on the psychological states and social perceptions of individuals, but also reveals the reflections of Turkish Cinema on social dynamics. Turkish Cinema was influenced by the liberal economy and the public experienced various depressions in this process; this situation was also reflected in the cinema. While Sunal's character Yusuf reinforces this understanding of social realism, he ironically mirrors the difficulties experienced by the people in the economic and cultural context and he presents his own unique attitude to his social environment without allowing environmental factors to turn into behaviour.

The aim

This study analyses the individual perception of social situations and reflects the psychology onto a specific circumstance as if it was brought from the birth of the individual or it is assumed that it was in the nature of him or her. The context presents that the person is a sensible mechanism that accumulates any interactive attitudes. The aim is to present those attitudes as individual and society interactions in the frame of psycho-social or socio-psychological studies by defining specific points.

Research Questions

As it is presented, that individual is a living mechanism that accumulated any data during the process of individual and social impacts or interactions. Thus, it is presented that the product of the study, what is handled in it, how it is explained related to its circumstances, what the sources are in those kinds of situations, and what kind of analyses are presented. During the study, the reader can find those answer for the frame of the study

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative approach to explore and explain the correlation between literature and sociology in the frame of social psychology. The study focuses on the connections of the terms with literature, sociology, and psychology. It reflects a specific work from the Modern Age to present how literature concerns itself with human, private, and public life experienced various depressions in the age of economic depression. It is aimed to present how social events and economic difficulties effect the individual's psychological situation and how they find a way of expression in literary works. The correlation between literature and social psychology gives a way to analyse the human experiments and challenges in the frame of qualitative understanding.

Data Collection

For this article, the data collected from specific articles, books, and literary works relate to the subject of this study. They are from different fields' journals, books, and specific works to support the approach in the frame of literary study.

Analysis: *Gülen Adam* (1989)

In this study, the correlation between literature and social psychology is criticised through a Turkish film, *Gülen Adam*, to reflect that the social life of every culture has a common valid issue: to have a problem with the future and to be irrelevant to this serious issue. It means that the literary dimension of an issue

has its various effects on social, economic, health, and psychological studies. A multidimensional assessment of a literary work provides that the reader could find the sources of some specific subjects.

In the film, Yusuf's character's constantly smiling state attracts the attention of Oktay, who is doing his associate professorship in the field of psychology. He pursues Yusuf, the main character of the film, for his academic study and becomes friends with him. Oktay believes that Yusuf will one day realise how painful the social difference is, how important the economic situation is, and that while he laughs at these events, he will surely cry at an event, and that he will confirm his own ideas and successfully complete his associate professorship. Moreover, he will clarify the idea of whether social-psychology is effective on the individual or not.

The whole story begins when Yusuf falls in love with Naciye, a beautiful girl, at first sight and confronts the fact that his economic situation prevents him from getting together with Naciye. Yusuf, who works as an assistant at the dentist, shows Naciye the dentures there and humorously explains which low-income people they belong to. And he tells this to Associate Professor candidate Oktay. Yusuf is the reflection of a naive and somewhat uninformed natural person who has not yet encountered the realities of the country. Naciye's father is a public servant and has a status of his own. In order to prevent unplanned urbanisation, he is eager to demolish the shanties in the area immediately after all the approvals and signatures he receives from the municipality. When he assumes that Oktay, who comes with Yusuf to ask for his daughter, is the suitor of his daughter, he likes this situation. He even thinks that Yusuf is a dentist friend of Oktay. However, when the situation becomes clear, Yusuf laughs when he says that he will not give his daughter to an ordinary and poor person. Because there is a father with future anxiety who decides the future of his daughter within seconds according to the financial status of an individual. This situation is not necessary for Yusuf who is not aware of social interaction. Naciye wants to commit suicide in reaction to her father and opens the kitchen gas. This situation upsets her father very much.

Naciye's tendency to punish her father with such a reaction causes her father to be too controlling by assuming both mother and father roles due to the lack of a mother figure and to react to situations by getting angry. In his book *Çocuk Psikolojisi*, Sefa Saygılı explains the situation as different orientation, passive character, problems in forming social bonds, and (just like Naciye did) a tendency towards crime or punishment in the process of gender perception and development of children in families where the father or mother figure is missing (Saygılı, 2007). This will also be mentioned in the 4th section: discussion as being influenced by each other in psychology. After this chastising process, Yusuf and Naciye get married without the consent of the father, who cares about social interaction, but the houses are rented in foreign currency in Türkiye's. Yusuf laughs again. He expresses that this has nothing to do with coming of age and wonders why renting houses in foreign currency is also applied to Turkish citizens. While Yusuf is shown as being no different from the situation, the audience is informed about this. Yusuf buys a house without a title deed from a landlord who is described with a term like mafia father. Naciye's father will demolish the house because he works in the municipality and Yusuf will laugh at this situation again. Since he leaves the dentist and works in the wood factory of an acquaintance, he builds a house like a caravan in front of her father's house in one night. The first step towards self-realisation as an individual in the social sense is completed. The need for shelter is realised. This house is on wheels. By the time the father takes the approval and signature procedures according to Yusuf's area, Yusuf has already changed the location of his house. The Father Officer turns this into an ambition. But Oktay still could not prove and complete his thesis. Yusuf moves his portable house to the rich area. Since the luxury houses in the area are also unauthorised, Yusuf will be comfortable here. And Naciye's father also gets his share of the wrecking crew and becomes homeless and moves in with his daughter and son-in-law in need of shelter.

The distorted urbanisation and livelihood problems that continued until the early 2000s gave way to debts that could not be repaid. Why is it that the most basic element in Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which emerged in the second half of the 20th century, in Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs for self-fulfilment as an individual, housing? Although Türkiye is a country with a critical role in the world in the political sense, why is it that the people in the economic sense still experience housing and subsistence problems at remarkable rates? In fact, if we say that the most basic reason or social perception is the formation of the perception of the individual according to the environment in which he/she is located and directing his/her life to the environment with this perception, the questions may be answered. Since the individual's ability to meet his/her physiological, psychological and social needs is directed according to his/her environment, the expectation and amount of need is determined according to the environmental standards.

Procedure

In this study, various books, journals, and literary works will be used as primary data. As the field of study has a qualitative approach, the sources that are given will be enough to provide literary samples to enlarge, explain, and support the study. The selected sources include especially contemporary literature era in terms of the presentation year of the film. The sources will provide examples by focusing on the work mentioning on literature, film and social psychology.

Findings

As an Overview of Social Psychology, it is better to inform the reader about the origin of the word 'psychology'. "Psychology is derived from the Ancient Greek psyche, meaning soul or nerve, and logia, meaning study or explanation, but today the word is more commonly used to describe the science of mind and behaviour" (Lakşe, 2014). Psychology is a concept that examines the human mind and the transformation of individual and social behaviour in the process of processing facts and information in the human mind. As a framework that contributes especially to sub-studies and examines society and the individual, it is a phenomenon that deals with the mental perception and behavioral processes of the individual in the social sense together with detailed observations and environmental factors. Therefore, the social psychology framework can be literally presented as turning the individual into behaviour in terms of interaction and interaction.

Social psychology is the field of study that deals with the cause and interaction of society and individual behaviour within a specific framework. It focuses on how we perceive other people; how we react to each other and how we are affected by being in social situations. Sometimes it deals with what we think about other people, sometimes how we are affected collectively or individually, and sometimes how we take a behaviour from our culture and how we reflect it (Kayaoğlu, 2019). In the definition of social psychology, it should be especially noted that every culture, every language and every society has its own discourse and social perception, which is a discursive one. In every society, it is the main examination framework of social psychology to focus on the individuals who make up that society and to examine their relationships with each other and the behaviour they form according to these relationships (Kağıtçıbaşı, 2014). Society directing the individual, the individual being influenced by the society and according to these, issues such as morality, belief, thought and behaviour become the fields and subjects of study under social psychology

The sense of humour of the character Yusuf is a psychological situation that defines Yusuf's perception of life from his angle or deteriorated psychological behaviour. The situation is ironical as he laughs at anything in his life. The detailed sides of his mentality present a deep analysis of the human psyche.

However, the empirical study of humor holds many interesting surprises. Although it is essentially a type of mental play involving a lighthearted, nonserious attitude toward ideas and events, humor serves a

number of "serious" social, emotional, and cognitive functions, making it a fascinating and rewarding topic of scientific investigation (Martin, 2007, p.1).

The field of psychology examines humour as a significant branch of it by focusing on the individual and social surroundings of him. The focus is especially on infancy to childhood, and the lifespan of the one is continually detected and analyzed. The effect of it is accepted as a mental and physical process; also, it is a biological basis rooted in genes. In his book, *The Psychology of Humour: An Integrative Approach* (2007), Rod A. Martin defines the process of the acquaintance of humour within the individual's cultural norms, affecting his social interactions and creating a sense of humour accordingly. In Martin's study, humour is divided into four parts: a social context, a cognitive-perceptual process, an emotional response, and the vocal-behavioral expression of laughter. The character Yusuf's psychological process is a way of creating mirth to provide a social interaction, and also the more significant one is that it is a way of relieving tension by regulating emotions and coping with stress. It means the first-level social context is stressful, and it goes into a perceptual process and produces a laughter as a reaction or expression.

In defining social-psychology, the mental and behavioral processes of the individual are influenced by environment and culture. Within the framework of this discipline, social psychology tries to understand and present the variability of the individual among social groups. In other words, while social psychology examines the individual in society, it examines the basic components, cultural elements, interaction between groups, emotional definitions, the sequence of translating them into behaviour and attitude, and ultimately the application areas of these. In the formation of social psychology, the processes of influencing and being influenced by the individual have a significant place. Because it can positively or negatively affect the basis for the realisation of behaviour and attitude, which is the ultimate point. In the film *Gülen Adam*, Yusuf is presented as an exception, because he is not an individual who is affected by his environment, on the contrary, he looks at every situation with a unique reaction. In fact, the character of Yusuf presents the norms, that is, the socio-psychological situation of the Turkish people, to the audience as a laugh. This is his fourth level of sense of humor perception.

Results and Discussion

In psychology the process of influencing and being influenced by each other is handled in the frame of social-psychology. David Myers begins Chapter 5, of his book *Social Psychology*, with the preface statement that people are the same by birth but different by tradition (Myers, 2014). People start to turn their innate instinctive behaviors such as hunger, crying, laughing or being surprised into a behavioral state depending on the context with their social and individual interactive relationships. Apart from our biological characteristics that we bring with our genes, we continue this continuity process uninterruptedly in the process of being affected by culture and behaviour with the environment and social commitment we are in. Culture is undoubtedly one of the leading elements in influencing social-psychology in this interaction process. Permanent behaviors, ideas, attitudes and traditions that are shared and transmitted from one generation to the next are the underlying elements of culture, that is, social-psychology. The name of this interaction is the social order, i.e. society, which influences the individual's social-psychology in the development, progress, in short, in the formation processes from the outside to the inside, that is, in positive or negative interactions and in the acquisition of behaviour by the individual. "Human beings are under the influence of those around them, the countless events and people they encounter every day, the socioeconomic and socio-cultural conditions in which they live, traditions and laws, the physical environment and many other factors" (Kağıtçıbaşı et al., 2014, p.220). In her book *Dünden Bugüne İnsan ve insanlar: Sosyal Psikolojiye Giriş*, Prof. Dr. Çiğdem Kağıtçıbaşı states that although there are common factors, people may have been affected differently from each other in the process of becoming a person according to the process and degree of influence of the conditions. Therefore, the socialization process of

a person may also be different. In this context, in Sunal's films, social change through character relationships, social norms and values, humour and criticism may seem superficial, but it is dealt with in depth from a socio-psychological point of view, just like in this study. These interactions are shaped especially through the conflicts of individuals in the inner and outer world. The struggles of ordinary people and their social status determine the dynamics of the relationships between them. For example, the main characters usually belong to the lower class of society, and while trying to cope with economic difficulties, they question social norms through their relationships with other characters around them. The films show how the characters affect each other within the framework of social norms and values. As Sunal's characters clash with the expectations of society, the consequences of these conflicts are revealed on both individual and social levels.

As an example, a character's stance against the general view of the society can create change on other characters. Characters are caught between their own dreams and social realities. These conflicts deepen the interactions, as one character's inner problems affect the behaviour and attitudes of other characters. This situation shows the audience the complexity of human psychology and the consequences of social interactions. Humour is an important tool of interactions in Sunal's works. Dialogues between characters and situation comedies make the audience think by presenting social criticism in a humorous language. In this context, humour is used as a tool to question the interaction between individuals and the general dynamics of society. Sunal's films also deal with the effects of individuals on the processes of social change. The experiences of the characters function as a mirror of social changes. Individuals have the potential to influence the people and society around them through the transformations in their own lives. In Kemal Sunal's films, the theme of 'influencing and being influenced by each other' is richly explored through the relationships between characters, internal conflicts and social norms. These interactions go deeper into human psychology and social dynamics by offering the audience both a thought-provoking and entertaining experience. In this respect, Sunal's works offer an important analysis of the socio-psychological structure of Turkish society.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Socio-psychological identification provides a broad frame for understanding how individuals think, feel, and behave in a social context. This approach improves a deep understanding aiming to solve the relationships between the individual and society. The film of Kemal Sunal, who was one of the modern Turkish cinema, presents the individual and social interaction of individual relations in a satirical way.

Within the context of psychological study, it explains that the individual approaches the events by laughing as learned helplessness and that the perception formed under this perception is that some social realities cannot change in the process of becoming conscious and that the individual's humorous attitude towards this immutability can create a more positive situation in daily life. The movie *Gülen Adam*, as the word 'adam' (man) suggests, presents the importance of the individual in society and his/her important place in the process of influencing and being influenced by holding a mirror to certain social situations from a different perspective. In addition to historical, romantic, or horror films, other films depicting social phenomena, such as *Gülen Adam*, have also come to life with the artist Kemal Sunal. The facts of life in a humorous way, such as jokes or stories, have features that make the audience laugh and think. The characters brought to life by the artist are often negatively affected and ostracized by society. Because while they have difficulty in keeping up with social norms, they also explain the process to the audience. However, this isolation is a valuable process for getting to know the society and the excluded individual. That process is the process of social-psychology and the individual represents social existence. Ordinary people, that is, any individual in society, or people who resist norms or are directly or indirectly affected

by them, have also been the subject of academic studies and presented to the audience in the artist's films, as in this study.

It can be concluded as the realization of humor has a processes such as input and output of the knowledge. They are cognitive and emotional products of interpersonal interactions in the social context. This situation is especially based on the individual social skill and competence. The same conditions may not be perceived in a same way by different people as it is occurred in Yusuf's different perception of humor as biological, psychological and , the most significant one, the social perception of sense of humor changes.

References

- Durmuş, İ. (2024). Organizational Overview of Maslow and Management Research. *Türk Psikolojik Danışma Ve Rehberlik Dergisi*, 14(72), 137–152. https://doi.org/10.17066/tpdrd.1332600_10
- Dacey, J. S., Mack, M. D., & Fiore, L. B. (2016). *Your anxious child: How parents and teachers can relieve anxiety in children*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Freeman, J.L, Sears, D.O, & Carlsmith, J.M . (2003). *Sosyal Psikoloji* (A. Dönmez,4rd ed.).İmge Kitapevi Yayınları (Orijinal baskı 1989).
- Lakşe, E., Bayrak, M. F., Bayrak, V., & Küpüşoğlu, M. (2014). *Psikoloji Kitabı*. Alfa.
- Kağıtçıbaşı, C., Cemalçılar, Z., & Karaöz, V. (2014). *Dünden Bugüne İnsan ve insanlar: Sosyal Psikolojiye Giriş*. Evrim.
- Kayaoğlu, A., Ö.A, Züleyha., Rüçhan, G. (2019). *Sosyal Psikoloji I*. Anadolu ÜniversitesiYayıncı
- Martin, R. A. (2007). *The psychology of humor: An integrative approach*. Elsevier Academic Press.
- Matsumoto, D. (2001). *Psychology and culture*. Wadsworth.
- Myers, D. G. (2014). *Social psychology* (11. baskı). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Forsyth, D. R. (2018). *Group dynamics* (7. baskı). Cengage Learning.
- Sarı, B. (2021). Yeni Sağ Siyaset, Ekonomi ve Toplum Anlayışının türk sinemasındaki izleri: Politik Komedi Filmleri Odağında Bir Değerlendirme. *Türkiye İletişim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, (38), 323–341.
- Saygılı, S. (2008). *Çocuk Psikolojisi: (0-7 yaş)*. Nesil.
- Tufan, Z. (2015). *Sosyal psikoloji*. Nobel Yayıncılık.

يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليين أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

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